

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

KEY DIMENSIONS OF WEB-BASED RESERVATION SYSTEMS IN MODERN TOURISM SECTOR

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Abstract

The main objective of this article is to examine the essential features and aspects of modern tourism reservation systems (TRS) in the rapidly evolving tourism sector. The tasks involved understanding the evolution of reservation systems from airline-centric origins to comprehensive platforms covering various tourism services. The study also examines the functional range of contemporary web-based reservation systems and the key features that these systems must have in order to fulfill the growing expectations of customers. Emphasis is placed on the latest crucial technological trends, such as cloud computing, mobile technologies, and social network integration, which must be integrated into web-based reservation systems. In conclusion, the research highlights the critical role of TRS in meeting the demands of a dynamic tourism landscape, offering insights into the multifaceted functionalities required for effective modern reservation systems.

Keywords: Tourism Reservation Systems, Computer Reservation Systems, Web-based reservation systems, cloud computing, mobile technologies.

Tourism Reservation Systems (TRS), commonly referred to as Computer Reservation Systems (CRS) or simply Reservation Systems, are the most widely utilized technology in the tourism business. These are fundamentally electronic systems implied to increase sales and provide rapid and accurate information on the availability, prices, and booking of the travel company's products and services. Originally developed and implemented by airlines to book airline tickets, reservation systems are now used to store and distribute information about tourism products and services, either directly or through intermediaries, and thus serve to book hotels, restaurants, plane tickets, tourist tours, cultural and sporting events, etc. The transmission of this information among many intermediaries and customers results in mergers and acquisitions, and therefore the development of Global Distribution Systems such as Amadeus, Sabre, Galileo, and Worldspan [1].

Today, computerized reservation systems are becoming a very important marketing component, through which interactions with tourists are stored and analyzed through multiple information channels, mostly electronic, and the information obtained serves to promote and offer a wide range of tourism products and services. Reservation systems also provide users with additional services and information such as insurance, excursions, currency exchange rates, health information, etc. [2].

Tourism reservation systems are now totally electronic, and most of them are web-based or online.

The functional scope of modern web-based tourism reservation systems is related to the latest trends in the development of world tourism and information technologies [3]:

- improved communication with the client through various communication channels;
- the concentration of offered tourist services in resorts or chains;
- presentation of services in real-time;

- the dynamics of tourist products, innovations, and changes in the tourism industry, which turn reservation systems into a powerful marketing tool for the promotion and distribution of tourist products;

- mobility of qualified personnel;
- higher demands from customers, a wider range of needs, imposition of a higher standard of services;

- development of eco and cultural tourism;
- globalization and increased competition in the industry.

Web-based reservation systems must accomplish the following essential functions to meet the rising expectations set by the environment, competitors, and customers [4], [5], [6], [7], [8]:

- **tourist product and service presentation** - reservation systems are the most important source of information about the products and services offered by sector suppliers. Each category of travel-related businesses provides unique content describing their products or services. Airlines, for example, only require providing information on the flight schedule, price, fees, and route, whereas hotels provide much more information about accommodation - type, size, and amenities of rooms, additional services, discounts, etc. This presentation is mostly done in web-based reservation systems via the corporate website or worldwide reservation system sites.

- **reservation** - the primary function of reservation systems. A record is created for each guest/passenger during this process. It holds all of the client's information, which is transmitted to the other information systems involved in its servicing. Furthermore, the data allows for the creation of a profile for each user and the delivery of customized offers based on their preferences, needs, and activities. A fundamental requirement for web-based reservation systems is that the reservation process occurs in real-time, with users not having to wait for a response to their requests and inquiries.

The information regarding available dates, flights, hotels, and places is retrieved from the travel company's website, and the customer can book them directly.

- ***inquiries regarding prices, fees, and tickets*** - this varies depending on the type and complexity of services provided. For example, the price and additional charges for flights vary depending on the category of the ticket, the day the reservation is made, the route, the number and duration between transfers, etc. In actuality, airline fares are calculated separately for each passenger and might alter daily. Other suppliers' costs, such as hotels and restaurants, are largely stable and offers rarely vary.

- ***a multi-language and multi-currency operation***, allowing foreign travelers to book through the website. It is recommended that the site supports as many languages and currencies as possible and that it adapts automatically upon detecting the user's locale. If this is not practicable, the web-based reservation system must be available in English, and currency conversion in standard international currencies such as the dollar and euro must be available.

- ***generation and management of vouchers online***, as well as integration with external systems offering vouchers.

- ***online payment*** via a variety of payment instruments such as debit and credit cards, PayPal, electronic payment systems, etc. Customers can pay for their reservations right away and ensure their fulfillment, and tourism companies can be confident in the visitors' ability to pay.

- ***displaying a calendar*** on the site from which potential consumers may see summary information about reservations made, available seats, and pricing not just for the present date, but also for weeks and months ahead, to plan a trip, hotel accommodation, etc.

- ***sending automated e-mail messages*** to confirm reservations, notify customers of reminders, refuse or be unable to service the reservation, schedule changes, travel suggestions, etc.

- ***additional details on the travel and accommodation region*** - visa and health regulations, trade shows, attractions, currencies, etc.

- ***a system for managing the various channels*** via which the travel company's information is provided. It is useful for tourism organizations that offer their products and services through multiple reservation systems, as it allows for the avoidance of duplicate reservations; for this purpose, information about available places is automatically updated to all systems with which the company is connected.

- ***display of various queries and reports*** regarding reservations by days, months, and years, sales, payments, marketing campaign effectiveness, client profiles, etc.

Modern tourism reservation systems must be in sync with the latest crucial technological trends, such as cloud computing, mobile technologies, and social network integration.

Cloud-based reservation systems have revolutionized the tourism industry by offering a centralized platform for managing bookings, availability, and pricing. These systems enable real-time access to information,

empowering customers to make instant reservations for flights, accommodations, and other services. Their flexibility allows businesses to automate processes, implement dynamic pricing strategies, and efficiently manage packages. The cloud infrastructure ensures scalability during peak seasons and provides a secure environment for storing sensitive customer data. With enhanced data analytics capabilities, tourism businesses can gain valuable insights into customer behavior, facilitating personalized services and ultimately improving overall operational efficiency and customer satisfaction in the rapidly evolving travel landscape. On the other hand, cloud services allow users to use the system from anywhere and at any time through their mobile device, with only an internet connection and a browser.

Without a doubt, one of the most noticeable trends in the recent decade has been the fast penetration of mobile technologies into all aspects of public life. Mobile devices, such as laptops and notebooks, tablets, and, especially, cell phones, are an integral part of everyday life for all people. Mobile technologies are also increasingly used in the booking of tourism products and services because of their ease of use, innovation, fast data transmission, and small size. The tourism reservation system must be integrated with mobile devices, which can be achieved by either optimizing the website for mobile use or developing its own mobile application.

Social networks are also playing an increasing role in the tourism industry. Furthermore, this industry was among the first to recognize the value of social media and incorporate it into its business practices [9]. Social media adds new channels to communicate with tourists, and most of them use the Internet as a source of information when planning their trips. Therefore, reservation systems must be integrated with marketing platforms, social media, and social networks. The presence of the global reservation system on sites like TripAdvisor, GetYourGuide, EventimGuide, Jollydays, Kochschule.de, or Viator is especially beneficial. New prospective customers have been reached, and new bookings can be generated.

In conclusion, the trajectory of Tourism Reservation Systems (TRS) signifies a pivotal transformation, positioning them as indispensable tools within the dynamic landscape of the tourism industry. The profound shift towards web-based reservation systems stands as a testament to the industry's proactive adaptation to the latest trends in global tourism and information technologies. These systems extend beyond their fundamental role of facilitating real-time reservations, emerging as integral components in the realm of marketing strategy. The inherent multifaceted functionalities embedded within TRS, encompassing features like multi-language support, seamless online payment capabilities, and easy integration with cutting-edge cloud computing and mobile technologies and expansive social networks, highlight the systems' remarkable adaptability. This flexibility is critical in satisfying the rising demands of both industry stakeholders and discerning customers, significantly contributing to the overall growth and sophistication of modern tourism practices.

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